

Analysis of the P5 Implementation at SMP IT YPI An-Nur in the Theme of Entrepreneurship

Revita YANUARSARI

Ella DEWI

LISNAWATI

Sari RAHAYU

Agus MULYANTO

Ika KARTIKA AF

Manuscript information:

Received: December 8, 2022

Revised: December 31, 2022

Accepted: January 3, 2023

Authors

Revita YANUARSARI
revita@uninus.ac.id
M.M.Pd., Universitas Islam
Nusantara, Indonesia

Ella DEWI
ella@staialfalah.ac.id
M.Pd., Universitas Islam
Nusantara, Indonesia

LISNAWATI
lisnawati.hilma@gmail.com
M.M.Pd., Universitas Islam
Nusantara, Indonesia

Sari RAHAYU
sarirahayu@staima.ac.id
M.Pd.I., Universitas Islam
Nusantara, Indonesia

Agus MULYANTO
agusmulyantouin@gmail.com
Dr., M.Pd., Universitas Islam
Nusantara, Indonesia

Ika KARTIKA AF
ikkaambu@gmail.com
Dr., M.Pd., Universitas Islam
Nusantara, Indonesia

Abstract

Freedom to learn is freedom of thought and innovation. The Independent Learning curriculum aims to strengthen students' character education through the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project program, where this is an Interdisciplinary Science Project that is contextual and based on community needs or problems in the educational unit environment. This study aims to (1) describe the implementation of a project to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students at SMP IT YPI An-Nur; (2) analyze the supporting and inhibiting factors in the implementation of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project at IT YPI An-Nur Middle School. The research approach used is qualitative with descriptive research methods. The subjects of this research were Principals, Teachers, and Students of SMP IT YPI An-Nur Grade VII SMP. The results of the study stated that in the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) activities, students experienced development after participating in the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project. Some of the abilities students gain include the ability to work together, creativity, problem-solving skills, and skills to make entrepreneurial products to foster an entrepreneurial spirit in students. The supporting and inhibiting factors for the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5) are implementing a character education culture, the presence of teachers who have good morals, and being in a positive environment. While the inhibiting factors are the lack of infrastructure provision and the teacher's lack of understanding of the P5 concept.

Keywords: Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project (P5), Entrepreneurship, Junior High School

Cite as: Yanuarsari, R., Dewi, E., Lisnawati, L., Rahayu, S., Mulyanto, A., & Kartika Af, I. (2023). Analysis of the P5 Implementation at SMP IT YPI An-Nur in the Theme of Entrepreneurship. *European Journal of Educational and Social Sciences*, 8(1), 1-11.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7853723>

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is a process of changing attitudes as well as the behavior of individuals or groups of people to mature humans through independent learning to develop self-abilities, managing an attitude that cares about the student learning environment, encouraging students to be confident and adapts easily to the community environment (Baharuddin, 2021) in (Rizal et al., 2022). Indonesia is a nation with character; character is the value of each individual's behavior towards God Almighty, himself, others, the environment, and his country, which is formed from the thoughts, attitudes, feelings, words, and actions based on various other norms such as religion, laws, manners, culture, and customs (Muslich, 2011, p. 84). Forming the attitude or character of each individual, especially students as the nation's future, must be instilled from birth. Education will guide all natural forces that exist in all students so they can obtain the highest possible safety and happiness as individuals and as part of society (Dewantara, 2011). In RI Law Number 20 Article 3 of 2003, it is stated that national education functions to develop and shape the character of a dignified national civilization as an effort to educate the nation's life, develop the potential and abilities of students and shape them into individuals who believe, have a noble character, are knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic and responsible citizens (Mery et al., 2022).

Education is a strategic basis in the current era of globalization. The national education system on the border produces quality people who, according to some, will occupy strategic positions in all industries and society. However, it must be acknowledged that many of the assumptions that our education system will follow are that human resources are of low quality and will continue to sow moral damage in response to the diversity crisis., Mitigate and prevent multidimensional crises, especially in the face of unethical attitudes or behavior in society (Ngimadudin, 2021) in (Nurasiah et al., 2022). Indonesia's educational vision is to realize an advanced Indonesia that is sovereign, independent, and has personality through the creation of Pancasila students, as stated in the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation number 22 of 2020 concerning the Ministry of Education and Culture's Strategic Plan for 2020-2024, namely: Pancasila students are the embodiment of Indonesian students as students lifelong who have global competence and behave under Pancasila values, with six dimensions, namely: (1) faith, fear of God Almighty, and noble character, (2) global diversity, (3) cooperation, (4) independent, (5) critical reasoning, and (6) creativity (Rusnaini et al., 202, as cited in Fadillah et al., 2022). Through education, a person can develop knowledge, insight, values , and character, even though some are inherited from culture. This new educational model is conveyed through the impl

ementation structure of school programs, especially programs to promote the transition of academic units to improve the learning outcomes of students who attend good education in terms of cognitive (literacy and computing) and non-cognitive (character) competencies to achieve the Pancasila Student Profile (Mutiarra et al., 2022, as cited in Nurasiah et al., 2022).

In the independent curriculum, the Minister of Education, Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia, Nadiem Anwar Makarim, stated that strengthening student character education would be manifested by the Ministry of Education and Culture through various strategies centered on efforts to realize Pancasila Students (Ismail et al., 2021). According to (Wahyuni, 2022) on the independent curriculum, there are several terms for Pancasila student profiles, such as Pancasila student profiles, strengthening Pancasila student profiles, and projects to strengthen Pancasila student profiles (P5) (Kurniawaty & Faiz, 2022) which are now being echoed in every educational institution. The Pancasila student profile is the

expected graduate profile to demonstrate the character and competence that students are expected to achieve (Mery et al., 2022). *Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka* (MBKM) is an innovation that combines learning activities with the independent learning curriculum in driving schools. The presence of driving schools is the government's effort to improve the quality and quantity of education in the country (Ritonga et al., 2022). Thus the driving school is expected to become a forum and solution for school work programs to support the development of strengthening the profile of Pancasila students (Rizal et al., 2022). Strengthening the Pancasila student profile project is currently being implemented in educator units through the activator school program (*Program Sekolah Penggerak*) for both the elementary, middle and high school/vocational school levels (Rachmawati et al., 2022).

Several studies have revealed that the implementation of the development of strengthening the Pancasila student profile (P5) has been carried out, one of which is (Susilawati et al., 2021), which revealed that the Pancasila Student Profile is essentially one of the efforts to internalize Pancasila values in learning, has a significant role in implementing the Pancasila Student Profile in the new paradigm of learning, and being able to internalize the values of Pancasila in the application of the Pancasila Student Profile in the new normal era assisted by the *Kampus Mengajar* by applying it in the daily character that is built and enlivened in each student's self through school culture, learning intracurricular, curricular and extracurricular activities at school. Its implementation (Wijayanti et al., 2022) provides an overview and conclusion that school teachers have tried their best to carry out project activities based on directions and guidelines given by the agency or their representatives. Furthermore, the writing (Jufri, 2022) argues that "learning projects such as the *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika* Project in the prototype curriculum of driving schools are very appropriate for realizing the strengthening of the Pancasila student profile because students and educators are given ample and meaningful space to see directly (contextually) reality community life which is the object of educational study in schools. Other studies say that training activities to strengthen the Pancasila student profile project can be concluded to have succeeded in guiding 15 teachers and school principals to implement P5 in their respective schools. This success is demonstrated by their ability to plan projects to be carried out at the beginning of the 2022-2023 school year. In addition, it is necessary to study independently through the available digital platforms. (Hamidah, 2022). Regarding the guidebook for the implementation of the Pancasila profile project, the research (Zuriah & Sunaryo, 2022) said that the character values contained in the Pancasila profile project guidebook must be accompanied by examples of its application in project activities to strengthen Pancasila character. To support the realization of the Pancasila Student Profile, this study recommends that the government adjust the book's content according to the Pancasila educational nomenclature so that it is more relevant and representative of the latest learning outcomes.

Learning planning for the project to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students in implementing 21st-century learning oriented towards an independent curriculum, there are several stages, namely the school readiness stage, identifying themes that have been determined by the Ministry of Education and Culture, determining themes that are more specific according to conditions in the school environment, determining time allocation, creating project modules, making sub-elements and *assessments* (summative and formative) (Nisa', 2022). Citing his writings (Mery et al., 2022) which stated that in developing a project to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students, the Ministry of Education and Culture launched seven themes and developed them based on priority issues stated in the 2020-2035 National Education Roadmap, Sustainable Development Goals, and other documents that relevant. The five general themes launched for the

Elementary School level are Sustainable Lifestyle, Local Wisdom, Unity in Diversity, Engineering and Technology to Build the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and Entrepreneurship. The focus of P5 policy research is expected to strengthen character that can provide opportunities for students to learn about the surrounding environment, whether it is about climate change which is happening especially lately, anti-radicalism, mental health, culture, entrepreneurship, development technology, and democracy. Presidential Instruction Number 4 of 1995, concerning the National Movement to Socialize and Cultivate Entrepreneurship, mandates all Indonesian people and the nation to develop entrepreneurship programs. The government is well aware that the business world is the backbone of the national economy, so continuous efforts must be made to improve it. Through this movement, it is hoped that the entrepreneurial character will become part of the work ethic of the people and nation of Indonesia so that it can give birth to new entrepreneurs who are reliable, rugged, and independent (Mulyani, 2012).

Entrepreneurship education will encourage students and students to start recognizing and opening businesses or entrepreneurship. The mindset always oriented to being an employee is reversed to becoming oriented to finding employees. Thus entrepreneurship can be taught by instilling entrepreneurial values that will shape character and behavior for entrepreneurship so that students can later be independent in work or business. Referring to previous research conducted by Dewanti (2015), the school's efforts to develop students' entrepreneurial spirit are the existence of intra-curricular activities in the curriculum implemented by schools, such as craft lessons, entrepreneurship, and other productive subjects. Schools' role is enormous in forming students' entrepreneurial skills. This can be seen from the various programs jointly prepared at the beginning of each new academic year.

These programs include student commerce, entrepreneur zone, culinary corner, entrepreneurs sharing inspiration, and gardening. Implementation is carried out in teaching and learning, extracurriculars, and entrepreneurship subjects. This research can inform other schools about implementing and cultivating students' entrepreneurial spirit. The growth of students' entrepreneurial spirit is included in the learning process. The learning process cannot be carried out with only one activity program. Entrepreneurship programs should be carried out on an ongoing basis to develop students' entrepreneurial spirit (Maknuni, 2021). Based on research conducted by Nugraha et al. (2022), the implementation of entrepreneurship education at SD Negeri Margaluyu through self-development by applying creative character, being independent, being able to solve problems, never giving up, good financial management, and socializing with people.

Meanwhile, (Rusmana et al, 2020) said that there is a significant influence between 21st-century digital skills on personal entrepreneurial effectiveness and entrepreneurial academic competencies, both directly and indirectly mediated by entrepreneurship education. So that it can be concluded from several studies above that entrepreneurial activities in schools can foster students' entrepreneurial spirit. This is in line with the purpose of the Pancasila profile project, namely, to foster the entrepreneurial character of students in schools.

One of the schools implementing the strengthening of the Pancasila student profile project is the IT YPI An-Nur Middle School. The Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project is a co-curricular activity in which one of the themes of the activity is Entrepreneurship. Through activities with the theme of entrepreneurship, students can foster an entrepreneurial spirit to increase students' interests, aspirations, and learning achievements and increase student participation in school. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the implementation of the Pancasila

Student Profile Strengthening Project in fostering students' entrepreneurial spirit. The results of this research are expected to be able to provide information and input for operational management working groups at the school, city/regency, provincial, and related central levels in cultivating an entrepreneurial spirit through the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project. The form of strengthening the Pancasila student profile is guided by the aim of character building, one of which is the introduction of strawberry cultivation entrepreneurial activities to students.

Based on the description of the problem above, the researcher feels the need to examine the entrepreneurial dimension further so that it can be developed in a project to strengthen the Pancasila student profile in class VII students at SMP IT YPI An-Nur. The purpose of writing this article is to conceptually describe the importance of implementing the Pancasila student profile strengthening project in developing entrepreneurial character on the theme of entrepreneurship in class VII students of SMP IT YPI An-Nur.

2. METHODOLOGY

The research method used is descriptive through a qualitative approach. This method was used because it was in accordance with the problems studied, namely to find out and describe the impact of implementing the Pancasila student profile strengthening project in fostering the entrepreneurial spirit of students so that it became one of the solutions in overcoming the problem of degradation of students' motivation to take part in face-to-face learning at school. Collecting data by observation and interviews, where the researcher digs up information about the desired data. The location of this research is YPI An-Nur IT Middle School, Jalan Karang Anyar, Mekarmulya, Garut City, Garut Regency. The research subjects used as data sources in this study were the academic community in the IT YPI An-Nur Middle School environment. The sources needed to fulfill the data are as many as 4 (four) Principals who are called by code (A1), Vice Principals in the field of the curriculum are called by code (A2), Class Teachers are called by code (A3), then the researcher conducts data triangulation by 2 (two) Student representatives from 2 groups in this study the informants were called code (A4).

The selection of four data sources in this study was due to what was stated by Moleong (2017) that qualitative research does not use populations because qualitative research departs from some instances that exist in certain social situations. The results of the study will not be applied to the population but in transfer to another place in a social situation that has similarities with the social situation in the case being studied. This research was conducted through the identification results of the author's observations of the activities carried out by SMP IT YPI An-Nur. The instruments used were observation and interviews. The authors then analyzed the data from the interviews through data reduction, presentation or display of data, and conclusion.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Implementation of *Entrepreneur Day* to Grow Entrepreneurial Values in Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles

The learning process in schools is an activity that can foster students' knowledge, skills, and character, so learning activities must be able to strengthen or even develop them. According to Sadewa (2022), the independent learning curriculum that is now implemented in every educational institution is a curriculum that was created to be able to heal and improve learning activities due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

Citing guidelines from the Education Standards, Curriculum and Assessment Agency of the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia (BSKAP,

2022), Education units are optional to carry out all the capacity strengthening listed on this page. In the learning process, academic units can adjust strengthening topics to the needs and readiness to empower themselves gradually and continuously. There are many projects to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students that can be selected by academic units, one of which is entrepreneurship. On the theme of entrepreneurship, students identify local economic potential, the problems in developing this potential, and its relation to environmental, social, and community welfare aspects. Through this activity, creativity and entrepreneurial culture will be developed. Students also gain insight into future opportunities, are sensitive to community needs, become skilled problem solvers, and are ready to become professional workers with integrity. This theme is intended for SD/MI, SMP/MTs, SMA/MA, and equivalent levels. (Because the SMK/MAK level already has Creative Projects and Entrepreneurship subjects, this theme is not an option for the SMK level.). An example of contextualizing the theme of entrepreneurship that can be done is to make products with local content that have marketability. The detailed explanation regarding the project to strengthen the Pancasila student profile is as follows:

Figure 1. Guidelines for Project Development Guidelines for Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles (2022)

Based on findings in the field, it was found that in the independent curriculum, there is a division of phases or levels of development that are adjusted to the characteristics, potential, and needs of students. As quoted from the article (Wahyuni, 2022), the progress of this project is inseparable from the school's readiness to implement the independent curriculum. The readiness stage is divided into 3: the initial, developing, and advanced (Ismail, Suhana, & Zakiah, 2021). During the P5 implementation of SMP IT YPI An-Nur, the initial preparations began, namely starting to implement the independent curriculum in the 2022/2023 school year. Previously, the school had prepared a project plan, but it was still relatively new as well as educators in the education unit, on average, are new to project learning. The implementation of P5 at SMP IT YPI An-Nur was motivated by a form of participation in the awareness and development of entrepreneurial attitudes for students at a young age, taking into account the function of the school as an institution that forms the knowledge, attitudes, and skills needed for life in the world of work. Educational institutions, especially schools as the second educational institution for students after the family, must provide the introduction, guidance, and assistance to students in recognizing, understanding, and cultivating noble values in the theme of entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurial activities are expected to foster an attitude of cooperation and improve the integrity and ethics of students. They are referring to P5 activities (Wahyuni, 2022). The steps in implementing P5 itself require a gradual arrangement, starting with problem identification, then continuing with project design, then the implementation stage. They are finally filled with reflection and evaluation of activities. Creative teachers must involve students in every design and practice of projects and learning (Faisal Fahri & Darwin, 2022). The P5 activity at YPI An-Nur IT Middle School raised the potential of Natural Resources from the surrounding environment. This P5 activity is carried out through in-class learning and extracurricular activities, where students are given direction and knowledge about the projected theme. The Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project is a co-curricular activity that is cross-subject learning using a project-based learning approach. Students are trained to investigate, solve problems, make decisions, and produce products or actions. Co-curricular activities aim to deepen and enrich the subject matter that has been implemented in intra-curricular activities. Co-curricular activities can be carried out through group activities or individually. Co-curricular activities can be carried out in an integrated manner with other subjects.

Referring to the various modules of the Pancasila project, one of which is the Project Module Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles Entrepreneurship Theme of SMAN 1 Dlingo with the title "Creative Fruits Based on Local Cultural Inspiration". The program determination in this module is based on local cultural inspiration, namely building awareness, exploring self-potential and regions, as well as empowering the knowledge and skills they have in developing entrepreneurship (Dlingo, 2022). The natural resource used as material for P5 activities at YPI An-Nur IT Middle School is Strawberry fruit which is abundant in the surrounding environment. The importance of implementing the project to strengthen the Pancasila student profile (P5) to develop entrepreneurial character and the cultivation of local natural resources in class VII students of SMP IT YPI An-Nur is the primary basis for implementing Entrepreneur Day *learning*. At the planning stage, the teacher arranges learning tools in modules entitled strengthening the Pancasila student profile. The module is used as a basis and guided in the implementation of learning. The participants did this to minimize errors in strengthening character education (Khoirinnida & Rondli, 2021; Shokib Rondli, 2022).

The implementation stage of Entrepreneur Day at SMP IT YPI An-Nur consists of 10 stages, including:

a. Project Activity Socialization Stage

At this stage, the teacher explains the implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile Project (P5) at SMP IT YPI An-Nur. It also socializes the project agenda to be carried out as Entrepreneur Day.

b. Group Formation Stage

At this stage, the teacher accompanies students in forming groups.

c. Entrepreneurial Character Recognition Stage

At this stage, students are directed to explore the meaning of entrepreneurship so that students can recognize the characteristics of an entrepreneur and can understand the basics of entrepreneurship and decision-making. At this stage, the activities carried out are the introduction of entrepreneurial themes, discussions related to students' expectations for this implementation, exploring students' knowledge related to students' initial entrepreneurial knowledge, working on quizzes about entrepreneurial attitudes, watching documentation of entrepreneurial figures, and identifying the attitudes they have an entrepreneur in the show.

d. Stages of Recognizing Regional Potential

At this stage, students are directed to observe the natural resources in the Mekarmulya area and the environment around SMP IT YPI An-Nur.

e. Stages of Finding Information

At this stage, students are asked to identify consumer needs, in this case, other students at SMP IT YPI An-Nur, through observation and interview techniques to get information embodied in consumer needs data. From the identification of needs, students who will carry out entrepreneur day can conclude consumer needs so that they can plan what products to make, what kind of product creations, what kind of packaging, and the number of products to be marketed.

f. Stages of Exploring and Developing Ideas

At this stage, students make Strawberry creation ideas according to the results of the initial identification and design processed strawberry creations based on local cultural inspiration. The designs are made with the aesthetic values and regional characteristics of Mekarmulya in mind so that consumers are attracted to the products to be marketed.

g. Planning and calculating stage

Students prepare plans for goods to be sold in the entrepreneur day project learning at this stage. At the same time, the teacher guides students on how to calculate the introductory price needed for the procurement of trade goods. Besides that, it also reminds students to pay attention to the buying ability of visitors.

h. Stages of Designing Sales Floor Plans and Presentation

At this stage, the teacher accompanies students when discussing sales location plans, including designing and arranging merchandise and decorating the sales area to make it more attractive.

i. Entrepreneur Day Implementation Stage

At this stage, the teacher asks students to prepare the tools and materials needed and organize the products to be sold. Then, the teacher asks students to record the number of items sold, and the rest of the students design the implementation of entrepreneur day by complying with the Health protocol.

j. Reflection Stage

At this stage, the teacher asks students to reflect by making reports and journals about implementing entrepreneurship. In the written report, students write down the activities that have been carried out from the initial stage to completion. Students must also write down the obstacles encountered during the entrepreneurial process. Then students are asked to make notes on the results of their reflections and ask student representatives to express the results of their reflections. This is in line with the opinion of Patton (2012) and Gómez et al. (2017), who stated that project-based learning is project-based learning that is based on student activities starting from designing, planning, and implementing projects to producing output. Thus the stages of implementing entrepreneur day project learning benefit students in motivating and increasing problem-solving, resource management, and collaborative skills.

In the Project to Strengthen Pancasila Student Profiles (P5) activities, students experienced development after participating in the Project to Strengthen Pancasila Student Profiles. Some of the abilities students acquire include the ability to cooperate, creativity, problem-solving skills, and skills in making entrepreneurial products to foster an entrepreneurial spirit in students. This study's results were aligned with the results of previous research conducted by Cahyani et al. (2019). Planning entrepreneurship training for students is carried out every six months and every

day. The planned aspects include human capital, finance, production, and marketing. The planning steps are conducting a SWOT analysis, then determining the business target and the strategy to be carried out. Then in line with the opinion of (Mulyani, 2014), who said that the entrepreneurship education project-based learning model applied in the experimental class increased entrepreneurial attitudes, interest in entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial behavior, and student achievement. The Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project has been significantly successful in cultivating an entrepreneurial spirit and developing students' abilities. Quoted from the writings of Noviani et al. (2022) which said that the results of this study were also in line with those (Cheung, 2008), which said that in the learning process, students need to be trained in how to recognize and identify local potential which is a regional advantage and be able to develop it through the entrepreneurial project. As in Hong Kong, the entrepreneurship program introduces teaching strategies into traditional classrooms with contextual learning. Students must set up and run their businesses, write business plans, and analyze fundamental business success factors.

3.2 Supporting Factors and inhibitor Project Learning *Entrepreneur Day* to Grow Entrepreneurial Values in Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles

Supporting factors that support the implementation of *Entrepreneur Day* to Grow Entrepreneurial Values in Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles are (1) School Culture. Schools have implemented school culture in strengthening education characteristics such as a culture of discipline, Friday sharing, obligatory prayers in congregation, and Dhuha prayers so that students have a commendable character provision. However, furthermore, it is necessary to strengthen character education in schools. (2) Teachers. Teachers have demonstrated good morals in everyday life because the role and influence of an educator on students are influential in cultivating good character values. (3) Environmental (external) supporting factors in the environment, SMP IT YPI An-Nur is in a positive environment to direct students to have characteristics such as Pancasila values. As for the factors that hinder the implementation of *Entrepreneur Day* Project Learning to Grow Entrepreneurial Values in Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles, namely: (1) Inadequate facilities and infrastructure, so that teachers are not maximal in using learning media so that the teaching and learning process is more effective, supporting facilities and infrastructure that should be utilized by several teachers in the teaching and learning process, namely LCD, laptop, internet, several reference books which should be a supporting factor for the success of the learning process. (2) The teacher's understanding of P5 is not yet comprehensive, some are still apathetic about changing terms in the curriculum, and there is no output from P5 in concept and practice. Several inhibiting factors in the implementation of learning projects to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students, so YPI An-Nur IT Middle School has not carried out these activities optimally. So SMP IT YPI An-Nur makes solution plans in developing learning projects to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students by providing improved facilities and infrastructure to support learning, providing understanding to teachers that learning activities must be integrated and provide meaning for today's and tomorrow's lives, as well as facilitating teachers for training activities that can increase teacher competence in learning to strengthen the Pancasila student profile.

4. CONCLUSION

The objectives, content, and learning activities of the project cannot be separated from the objectives and intracurricular subject matter. At the junior high school level, the Pancasila

Student Profile Strengthening Project was carried out in three projects with three different themes. The projects that are held must also refer to the dimensions of the development of the Pancasila student profile, the principles in question are activities that must be holistic, contextual, educator-centered, and exploratory. It can be concluded from the explanation above that the implementation of the project to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students at SMP IT YPI An-Nur has been carried out according to the independent learning curriculum guide.

In the Project to Strengthen Pancasila Student Profiles (P5) activities, students experienced development after participating in the Project to Strengthen Pancasila Student Profiles. Some of the abilities students acquire include the ability to cooperate, creativity, problem-solving skills, and skills in making entrepreneurial products to foster an entrepreneurial spirit in students. However, there must be reinforcement, so those project activities to strengthen the Pancasila profile are maximally carried out to create students with character according to Pancasila values.

The supporting and inhibiting factors for implementing the project to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students at SMP IT YPI An-Nur have implemented a character education school culture such as a culture of discipline, the presence of teachers who demonstrate good morals in everyday life, and are in a positive environment. In contrast, the inhibiting factors are the lack of provision of infrastructure that teachers can utilize and the teacher's lack of understanding of the concept of the Pancasila student profile strengthening project. So that schools are required to be more active in facilitating teachers to take part in training related to projects to strengthen Pancasila student profiles as an effort that can support teacher knowledge and skills in schools.

REFERENCES

- BSKAP, KR (2022). Guide to the Development of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project.
- Cahyani, SSA, Timan, A., & Sultoni, S. (2019). Management of Entrepreneurship Training for Students in Kampoeng Kidz. *Journal of Educational Administration and Management*, 2(1), 001–009. <https://doi.org/10.17977/um027v2i22019p1>
- Dewanti, W. (2015). The school's efforts in developing students' entrepreneurial spirit (a case study on boutique fashion students at SMK N 6 Semarang), Thesis, Faculty of Engineering, Semarang State University: Semarang.
- Dlingo, S. 1. (2022). Project Guide to Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles.
- Fadillah, S., Wiwit, & Aisyah. (2022). Improving Students' Understanding of Social Arithmetic Material Through the Project Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles. *Journal of Mathematics Education*, 13(2), 167–176. <http://ojs.uho.ac.id/index.php/jpm>
- Hamidah, J. (2022). Training on Project Preparation for Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles for Principals and Elementary School Teachers in Banjar-South Kalimantan District. *JURNAL CEMERLANG: Community Service*, 4(2), 259–271. <https://doi.org/10.31540/jpm.v4i2.1625>
- Jufri, M. (2022). Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project. In *Eureka Media Aksara*. <https://medium.com/@arifwicaksanaa/pengertian-use-case-a7e576e1b6b>
- Maknuni, J. (2021). Elementary School Strategies in Fostering Students' Entrepreneurial Spirit Strategies for Fostering Entrepreneurship Value on Students in Elementary School.

- CONTEXTUAL Scientific Journal*, 2(2), 9–16.
- Mery, M., Martono, M., Halidjah, S., & Hartoyo, A. (2022). Student Synergy in the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project. *Basic Edu Journal*, 6(5), 7840–7849. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicdu.v6i5.3617>
- Mulyani, E. (2012). Model of Entrepreneurship Education in Primary and Secondary Education. *Journal of Economics and Education*, 8(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.21831/jep.v8i1.705>
- Nisa', Z. (2022). Implementation of Independent Curriculum-Oriented 21st Century Learning Skills in Learning Projects to Strengthen Pancasila Student Profiles at SMP Al-Falah Deltasari Sidoarjo (pp. 1–25).
- Noviani, L., Wahida, A., & Umiatsih, ST (2022). Entrepreneurship Project Implementation Strategy at SMA Negeri 1 Sumberlawan. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Business*, 27(1), 60. <https://doi.org/10.20961/jkb.v27i1.58934>
- Nugraha, D., Wulandari, MA, Yuningsih, E., & Setiani, N. (2022). Formation of Student Character through the Entrepreneurship Program in Elementary Schools. *Basicedu Journal*, 6(4), 6754–6762. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v6i4.2974>
- Nurasiah, I., Marini, A., Nafiah, M., & Rachmawati, N. (2022). Value of Local Wisdom: New Paradigm Project, Mobilizing School Program to Realize Pancasila Student Profiles. *Basicedu Journal*, 6(3), 3639–3648. <https://jbasic.org/index.php/basicdu/article/view/971>
- Rachmawati, N., Marini, A., Nafiah, M., & Nurashiah, I. (2022). Project for Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles in the Implementation of Prototype Curriculum in Elementary Schools. *Basicedu Journal*, 6(3), 3613–3625. <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicdu.v6i3.2714>
- Rizal, Y., Deovany, M., & Andini, AS (2022). Student Confidence in the Implementation of the Pancasila Student Profile Strengthening Project. *SOCIAL HORIZON: Journal of Social Education*, 9(1), 46–57.
- Rusmana, D., Murtini, W., & Harini, H. (2020). The Influence of 21st Century Digital Skills on Entrepreneurship Education to Improve Entrepreneurial Competence of Vocational High School Students. *Journal of Educational Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 8(1), 17. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jepk.v8n1.p17-32>
- Shokib Rondli, W. (2022). Growing Entrepreneurial Value in Strengthening Pancasila Student Profiles Through Project Market Learning. *Journal of Prakarsa Paedagogia*, 5(1), 111. <http://jurnal.umk.ac.id/index.php/JKP>
- Susilawati, E., Sarifudin, S., & Muslim, S. (2021). Internalization of Pancasila Values in Learning Through the Application of Pancasila Student Profiles Assisted by the Freedom to Teach Platform. *Technodic Journal*, 25(2), 155–167. <https://doi.org/10.32550/teknodik.v25i2.897>
- Wahyuni, WR (2022). Planning for the Implementation of the P5 Activity Module (Entrepreneurship) in Phase B at Banjarejo Sdn. *Proceedings of the Basic Scientific Conference (KID)*, p. 3, 1627–1634.
- Wijayanti, PS, Jamilah, F., Herawati, TR, & Kusumaningrum, RN (2022). Strengthening the Preparation of the Pancasila Student Profile Project Module at SMA Level Driving Schools. *Abdimas Nusantara*, 3(2), 43–49. <http://ejurnal.unim.ac.id/index.php/abdimasnusantara/article/view/1715%0Ahttp://ejurnal.unim.ac.id/index.php/abdimasnusantara/article/download/1715/705>
- Zuriah, N., & Sunaryo, H. (2022). Teacher's Handbook PPKN in Elementary Schools. *Journal of Civic Law*, 7(1), 71–87.